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The Evaluation of Faculty of Education Students' Self-Efficiency Beliefs for Museum Education

Songül Mollaoglu¹

¹Faculty of Education, Sivas Cumhuriyet University, Türkiye.

E-mail: songulmollaoglu@gmail.com

Abstract

Museum education is a field that requires teachers to work with faith in school-museum cooperation. The aim of this study is to examine the self-efficacy beliefs of the students of the Faculty of Education of a university regarding museum education. 692 students studying at the Faculty of Education of a university participated in this study, which was carried out with the scanning model. The data of the research were obtained with the Student Identification Form (SIF) and the Self-Efficacy Belief Scale for Museum Education (SEBSFME). The average age of the students is 21.15 (SD: 1.801), 76% of them are women, most of them (69.7%) live in the city. 29% are in the 1st grade, 25.7% are in the 4th grade. 26.4% of the students are in Turkish Language Teaching, 21.2% in Social Studies Teaching and 15.9% in Art-Music Teaching. The mean score of SEBSFME is 80.86 (SD: 18.06). There was no significant difference between the SEBSFME mean score and variables such as age, gender, and place of residence. The difference between the students' grade level, department, visiting the museum and taking courses related to the museum was statistically significant. ($p < 0.05$). Self-efficacy belief towards museum education was found above the average scores of the Faculty of Education students. It is important for the students of the faculty of education, who are the teachers of the future, to develop their self-efficacy beliefs by being supported by museum education, which provides the development of important educational features such as questioning, research and examination.

Keywords: Museum, Education, Museum Education, Self-Efficacy, Belief, Visiting the Museum

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduce the Problem

The museum has services such as preserving, creating documents, publishing scientific publications and presenting these publications to the public. Since the 20th century, the main purpose of museums has been expanded as the transfer of culture and science to all segments of society. For this reason, the educational function of museums, besides collecting, protecting, examining, evaluating and exhibiting, has been shaped as a guide (Atagök 1982: 2; Maccario, 2002: 276).

Museology has led to a revolutionary development by being divided into sub-fields such as museum management, restoration - conservation, exhibition design, education, visitor relations, research, archiving and communication (Mensch, 2004:5). Participation in museums at the individual level can be a source of self-actualization, confidence and creativity, while at the societal level, such as social renewal, health, welfare, social assistance. It increases inter-individual and social cooperation in areas (Sandell, 2003:45).

The International Council of Museums (ICOM) emphasizes that the museum is an education, research and cultural center within its ethical codes. According to the ethical codes, museums are institutions that preserve, examine and promote the cultural and natural heritage by preserving their primary functions, but they must put their collections at the service of society and social development. Museum means knowledge, but at the same time it is the space to place, validate, develop and maintain knowledge (Griffin; 2004; Lord, 2007:13-19).

Visual culture is the gateway to the field of culture by communicating with various cultural elements through images. Museum education offers its visitors a visual learning environment that activates their own interpretation strategies and vocabulary (Greenhill, 2000). Therefore, using visual culture elements for the purpose of explaining the museum collection is among the priorities of the contemporary museum. In the educational arrangements in the museum, it should be emphasized by using visual culture elements that what the audience will see, how to determine the direction, what to focus on and why it is important to be remarkable. In this context, museum exhibitions also aim to share technological experiences and opinions, and there are educational auxiliary materials such as computer screens, hologram (digital counter), virtual travel, effectvision, three-dimensional scanning, simulator, three-dimensional modeling and digital applications (Karadeniz, et al. 2015; Kaschak, 2014).

Human success; behavior depends on the interaction between personal factors (such as attitudes, thoughts, beliefs) and environmental conditions (Schunk & Pjares, 2002). Therefore, people's beliefs about their own abilities are the determinants of their performance in a given situation. Accordingly, self-efficacy is not related to how competent an individual is in his skills, but to his belief in his own abilities. Self-efficacy beliefs determine how individuals feel, think, motivate themselves and behave (Akkoyunlu, Orhan & Umay, 2005: 1; Yeşilbursa & Uslu, 2014).

Bandura (1989) argues that self-efficacy belief determines the level of motivation of a person for a particular task. A person with high self-efficacy shows more persistence when faced with difficulties related to a particular task than a person with lower self-efficacy for that task. Strong belief in one's abilities increases persistence and effort. A person with high self-efficacy shows more persistence when faced with difficulties related to a particular task than a person with lower self-efficacy for that task. Strong belief in one's abilities increases persistence and effort. Since self-efficacy belief is an important concept that explains whether there is a difference between what individuals believe they can do and what they do (Kurt, 2012), contributing approaches can be developed to improve the ability of individuals by evaluating their self-efficacy perceptions in education faculty students, who are prospective teacher candidates. Thus, the perception of competence about the museums of the art educator who examines the works in the museum is important. The assessment of the self-efficacy belief of the arts educator allows them to evaluate their own learning and teaching processes. Evaluation of self-efficacy belief also allows the art educator to have an idea to make predictions about the level of cognitive self-sufficiency in educational environments and to make special judgments. With these judgments, art educators may experience success or limitations in their success by being positively or negatively affected in their studies in a special field (Bandura, 2012).

In the early 1990s, museum education was accepted as an interdisciplinary field that required a separate specialization and training, and in many countries, museology courses were opened in the field of visual arts education in universities and programs that provide museology and museum education formation was included (Kee - Kai, 2011:51). Museum education is a field that requires school-museum cooperation, and requires teachers to work with faith and make good planning. In order for students to benefit from museums at the highest level, an effective museum visit should be planned and the museum visit should be integrated with the curriculum. Teachers should also have sufficient knowledge and experience to integrate the museum visit and the curriculum; It is important that they create a good learning environment in order to turn it into a meaningful and effective learning experience. The fact that museum education requires good planning, associating with the program, integration and

cooperation reveals the necessity of revealing the self-efficacy beliefs of the education faculty students, who are the teachers of the future, about museum education. In this context, it is important to determine the self-efficacy beliefs of teacher candidates studying at education faculties towards museum education.

In this study, which aims to reveal the self-efficacy beliefs of the students of the Faculty of Education towards museum education, the following research questions were answered on the basis of this main framework.

1. What are the self-efficacy beliefs of education faculty students towards museum education?
2. Is there a significant gender difference in the self-efficacy beliefs of education faculty students towards museum education?
3. Is there a significant difference in the self-efficacy beliefs of education faculty students towards museum education according to grade level?
4. Is there a significant difference in the self-efficacy beliefs of education faculty students regarding museum education according to their departments?
5. Is there a significant difference in the self-efficacy beliefs of the education faculty students towards museum education, according to the status of taking courses related to the museum?
6. Is there a significant difference in the self-efficacy beliefs of education faculty students regarding museum education compared to their previous visit to a museum?

2. Method

This study was conducted with the survey research model, which is a quantitative research method. In descriptive studies that try to define any situation of interest, revealing a situation objectively is done with the scanning model (Karasar, 2009).

2.1 Participant (Subject) Characteristics

This study was carried out with 692 teacher candidates who continue their education in the Faculty of Education of a university and volunteer to participate in the study in the 2022-2023 academic year. The personal and educational characteristics of the students are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive Characteristics of Education Faculty Students (n:692)

Characteristics	n	%
Age;Min-Max.;Mean Age (Standard Deviation) Min-Max: 18-26 21.15 (SD:1.801).		
Gender		
Female	526	76.0
Male	166	24.0
Department		
Painting-Business Education	62	9.0
Music Teaching	41	5.9
Turkish Teacher	183	26.4
Social studies teacher	147	21.2
Pre-school teaching	60	8.7
Psychological Counseling and Guidance	35	5.1
English teacher	90	13.0
Science teacher	19	2.7
Elementary Mathematics Teaching	33	4.8
Classroom teaching	22	3.2
Class		
1. Class	201	29.0
2. Class	145	21.0
3. Class	168	24.3
4. Class	178	25.7
Residential area		
village-town	41	5.9

District	169	24.4
City	366	52.9
Big city	116	16.8

Table 1 shows the personal and educational characteristics of the students. The average age of students who are minimum 18 and maximum 26 years old is 21,157 (standard deviation: 1,801)years. 76% (526 students) of the students are female and 24% (166 students) are male. 26.4% of the students were Turkish Language Teaching, 21.2% Social Studies Teaching, 13% English Teaching, 9% Art Education Teaching, 8,7% Preschool Teaching, 5,9% Music Teaching, 5,1% Psychological Counseling and Guidance, 4,8%, Elementary Mathematics Teaching, 3,2% of them are studying in Classroom Teaching and 2,7% of them are studying in Science Education (Table 2). 29% of the students are 1st grade, 21% are 2nd grade, 24,3%3. grade and 25,7% are 4th grade students. On the other hand, 52,9% of the students live in the city and 5,9% in the village-town.

2.2 Measures and Covariates

2.3.1. Data Collection Tools

Two forms were used to collect data with the Student Introduction Form and the Self-Efficacy Beliefs Scale for Museum Education.

Student Introduction Form: In this form, there are questions about the personal and educational status of the student, such as the main art or department, class, age and gender, faculty, department, and museum experiences. *Self-Efficacy Beliefs Scale for Museum Education:* "The Self-Efficacy Beliefs Scale for Museum Education" developed by Yeşilbursa and Uslu (2014) on social studies teacher candidates consists of 24 questions. The Self-Efficacy Beliefs Scale for Museum Education was prepared in a 5-point likert type. The items in the scale are graded as "I am Completely Incompetent", "I am Inadequate", "I am Partially Sufficient", "I am Sufficient" and "I am Completely Sufficient", provided that they are scored from 1 to 5. The lowest score to be taken from the scale is 24 and the highest score is 120. As the score increases, self-efficacy belief in museum education increases. The Cronbach Alpha coefficient for the internal consistency of the items was found to be .96 (Yeşilbursa & Uslu, 2014). In this study, the Cronbach Alpha coefficient of the scale was .92.

Ethical Dimension

Institutional and necessary permissions were obtained from the Social and Human Sciences Ethics Committee of Sivas Cumhuriyet University in order to carry out this research.

Data analysis

Data analysis was done in SPSS (Ver: 22.0) package program. Descriptive statistics were applied to the data obtained in the study. Self-efficacy beliefs for museum education were determined by looking at the mean values of the groups with descriptive statistics. Arithmetic mean ($\bar{X}$) and standard deviation (Ss) were used to evaluate students' self-efficacy beliefs. In this study, it was analyzed that the skewness values of the scale were between -1 and +1, and as a result of the analysis, the significance value of the Shapiro-Wilk test was greater than 0.05, and the data were normally distributed. Due to the normal distribution, t-Test and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were applied for samples independent of parametric analysis techniques. In the statistical tests, 95% confidence interval and $p < 0.05$ were taken as significance level.

3. Results

This section contains the results obtained from the study. The personal and educational characteristics of the students and the results of the analyzes on the Self-Efficacy Belief Scale for Museum Education are given in this section.

Table 2: Average of Students' Self-Efficacy Beliefs for Museum Education (n:692)

Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
80.869	18.066	24	120

When the students' self-efficacy belief scores regarding museum education are examined in Table 2, it is seen that the average score is 80,869, the standard deviation is 18,066, and the min-max is 24-120 points.

Table 3: Students' Self-Efficacy Beliefs for Museum Education by Gender

Gender	Mean	Standard Deviation	Statistical Tests
Female	3.37	0.711	t:0.613
Male	3.33	0.873	p:0.540

As seen in Table 3, there is no difference between the students' self-efficacy beliefs regarding museum education according to their gender ($p > 0.05$).

Table 4: Self-Efficacy Beliefs for Museum Education According to Students' Departments

Departments	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sum of Squares	Sum of Squares	df	F	Sig.	Significant Difference					
1. Painting-Business Education	62	3.3871	.81400	Between Groups	17.894	9			2-4					
2. Music Teaching	41	3.3037	.64298						3-6					
3. Turkish Teacher	183	3.5147	.77341	Within Groups	373.665	682	3.629	.000						
4. Social studies teacher	147	3.6715	.57949											
5. Pre-school teaching	60	3.3274	.68032											
6. Psychological Counseling and Guidance	35	3.1750	.87010											
7. English teacher	90	3.6360	.82471											
8. Science teacher	19	3.0707	.73254											
9. Elementary Mathematics Teaching	33	3.4034	.46813											
10. Classroom teaching	22	3.2368	.91825											
Total										391.560	691			

When the average scores of self-efficacy beliefs related to museum education are examined according to the education faculties of the students in Table 4, it is determined that there is a difference between the departments ($F: 3,629$, $p: 0.000$). The difference between which groups was determined by Bonferroni multiple comparison test. It was determined that the difference was between social studies teaching and English teaching, in favor of social studies teaching, and between Turkish teaching and preschool teaching in favor of pre-school teaching.

Table 5: Students' Classes and Self-Efficacy Beliefs Regarding Museum Education

Class	n	Mean	Standard Deviation	df	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	p	Significant Difference (Scheffe)	
1.Class	40	76,2289	18,92055	Between Groups	167,777	80	2,097	1,681	,000	1-4
	169	79,5862	18,72372		762,459	611	1,248			

2.Class				Within Groups		
3.Class	366	81,9405	15,13916	Total	930,236	691
4.Class	116	86,1461	17,70221			

In Table 5, the total scores of students' self-efficacy beliefs towards museum education showed a significant difference according to the class variable [$F(1, 681), p < .001$]. Accordingly, a significant difference was determined between the self-efficacy beliefs of the students regarding museum education according to their classes.

Scheffe multiple comparison test was performed to see between which groups this difference was. According to the Scheffe multiple comparison test results, the mean scores of the students of the Faculty of Education in the first year of their self-efficacy beliefs towards museum education ($\bar{X} = 76,2289$) and the total score averages of the self-efficacy beliefs of the students in the fourth grade towards museum education ($\bar{X} = 86,1461$), a significant difference was found in favor of the Faculty of Education students studying in the fourth grade. Accordingly, fourth grade students have higher self-efficacy beliefs towards museum education.

Table 6: Students' Expressions Regarding Museum Experiences and Self-Efficacy Beliefs for Museum Education

Taking lessons about the museum	n	Mean	Standard Deviation	Statistical Tests
Yes	587	3,406	0.728	t:3.106
No	105	3,160	0.851	p:0.002
Making a museum visit				
Yes	591	3.420	0.719	t:4.383
No	101	3.070	0.867	p:0.000

In Table 6, students who took museum-related courses during their education were found to have higher self-efficacy beliefs about museum education than those who did not, and the difference was significant ($t:3.106, p:0.002$). On the other hand, the self-efficacy beliefs of museum visitors were found to be higher than those who did not, and the difference was statistically significant ($t:4.383, p:0.000$).

4. Discussion

In this study, which was conducted to examine the self-efficacy beliefs of museum education students of a university's Faculty of Education, the students' self-efficacy beliefs were found to be above the average. This average was found to be lower than the average score obtained in Woolfolk Hoy and Burke Spero (2005)'s study named changes in teacher efficacy during the early years of teaching: A comparison of four measures. In the study by Yeşilbursa and Uslu (2014), which evaluated the self-efficacy beliefs of social studies teacher candidates towards museum education, the average score was found to be higher than the average score obtained in this study. Friedman and Kass (2001) state that a teacher's perception of self-efficacy should extend beyond the classroom space. Museums are especially preferred in terms of enabling them to obtain information directly, to direct students towards research and examination, to actively participate in the learning environment, to realize permanent learning by doing and living, to motivate creative power and thought, and to enable the individual to express himself better by giving a feeling of a free environment.

In the literature, teachers with high self-efficacy beliefs are more persistent, more hardworking, more willing to teach, more understanding towards their students who make mistakes, have more goals and desires, have more teaching responsibilities, are more open to new ideas, have a higher level of planning and It is stated that they have organizational skills (Anderson, 2010; Tschannen-Moran & Woolfok Hoy, 2001). For this reason, it is important to make the necessary improvements in the curriculum for the students of the Faculty of Education, who are prospective teachers of the future, to have high self-efficacy in museum education.

In the study, the relationship between some personal and educational characteristics of the students who continue their education at the Faculty of Education and their self-efficacy beliefs about museum education was also examined. Accordingly, no difference was found between the students' gender, place of residence, faculty and department they studied, and the average scores of the self-efficacy beliefs scale regarding museum education. However, in this study, determining a significant difference in the self-efficacy beliefs of the students of the Faculty of Education towards museum education according to the grade level is another important result. According to the Scheffe multiple comparison test results, it was determined that the difference was between the first and fourth grades. A significant difference was found in favor of the Faculty of Education students studying in the fourth grade. Accordingly, fourth grade students have higher self-efficacy beliefs towards museum education. In some similar studies, while the class variable did not affect the self-efficacy beliefs of pre-service teachers (Akkuş, 2013; Aylar & Aksin, 2011, Bümen & Özyayın, 2013), in another study, there was a significant difference in favor of 3rd grade students in a study on museum education between 3rd and 4th grades. a difference was obtained (Yeşilbursa and Uslu, 2013). There are similar studies in which pre-service teachers' self-efficacy beliefs increase as their grade level increases (Şahin-Taşkın & Hacıömeroğlu, 2010; Pendergast et al., 2011). In this study, the Self-Efficacy Belief Scale for Museum Education was applied to all classes and a difference in favor of the fourth grades was obtained. The reason for this may be the possibility of increasing self-efficacy along with the skills gained periodically during university education. It is thought that this may be related to the fact that the candidates, who gradually adapt to the profession and gradually take an active role in the process with teaching practice and museum lessons, may begin to perceive themselves more positively in terms of museum education self-efficacy. It can be stated that the difference in different studies on the class variable is due to the sample change in the studies.

Another important data obtained in this study is that there is a difference between self-efficacy beliefs towards museum education according to the departments that train teachers in the education faculty. According to the interdepartmental multiple comparison analysis, it was determined that there was a positive difference between social studies teaching and English teaching, in favor of social studies teaching, and between Turkish teaching and preschool teaching in favor of preschool teaching. In the study conducted by Yeşilbursa and Uslu (2014) on third and fourth grade students of social studies teaching department, students' self-efficacy beliefs towards museum education were found to be high. Since the study was conducted on only one section in this study, no comparison with other sections was made.

In Saracaloğlu, Yenice, and Özden's (2013) study, "Examination of teacher self-efficacy perceptions, and academic locus of control of science, social studies and classroom teacher candidates," primary school students' perceptions of teacher self-efficacy were found to be high. Although there are many studies in the literature (Akkuş, 2013; Pendergast et al., 2011; Saracaloğlu, Yenice and Özden, 2013; Yılmaz and Egüz, 2015) on students studying in teacher-training departments, a limited number of studies (Yeşilbursa and Uslu, 2014) evaluating self-efficacy in museum education are available. For this reason, since this study is a study that evaluates self-efficacy in museum education by considering all departments and all classes of a teacher-training faculty, it is different from other studies and is thought to provide different inputs to the literature. While it is considered as one of the strengths of the study that teacher candidates studying in different branches make comparisons between self-efficacy beliefs about museum education and provide more detailed information in this way, it can be considered as a limitation of the study that the study is carried out only in the education faculty of a university. For this reason, necessary planning should be made considering the need for large-scale studies to be carried out in the future.

Another result obtained in this study is that students who took museum-related courses during their education had higher self-efficacy beliefs about museum education compared to those who did not, and those who visited the museum did not, and the difference was statistically significant. When the studies on the self-efficacy beliefs of teacher candidates for museum education were examined, it was found that the self-efficacy beliefs for museum education were found in favor of those who took the courses (Körükçü, 2019; Yeşilbursa and Uslu, 2014). It is an expected result that the museum education self-efficacy score averages of the teacher candidates who take museum education courses and visit museums are higher. On the other hand, the fact that the museum education self-efficacy belief is higher among the teacher candidates who visit the museum is similar to the literature knowledge (Dilmaç, 2016; Kıyıcı & Yiğit, 2013; Körükçü, 2019; Ustaoglu, 2012). In addition, Yılmaz and Egüz (2015) determined that museum visits increase the interest in the lesson in the learning process, develop the sense of

curiosity, and encountering the objects in the museum facilitates the reinforcement of the learned information, and also contributes to permanent learning. It is seen that the self-efficacy perception scores of the primary school teacher candidates are higher than the teacher candidates studying in other departments.

A person with high self-efficacy shows more persistence when faced with difficulties related to a particular task than a person with lower self-efficacy for that task. Strong belief in one's capabilities increases persistence and effort (Schunk, 1981; Zimmer and Ringle 1981; Bouchard, 1990, Kotaman, 2008). Therefore, in order to support the professional development of the students of the education faculty, who are the teachers of the future, it is important to give lessons and make practices related to the field of increasing self-efficacy. It should not be forgotten that a teacher with a high self-efficacy belief will raise students with this belief in the future.

In this case, as determined in this study, both taking the courses related to the museum and visiting the museum are the factors that positively affect the self-efficacy belief towards museum education, and these factors should be taken into account in educational institutions. Museum courses should be taught as a compulsory course in the relevant departments of the Education Faculties that train teachers. In addition, it is important that museums are used as an educational environment in all areas that train teachers, especially in the department of fine arts education.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

In this study, which was conducted to examine the self-efficacy beliefs of museum education and some personal and educational factors affecting the students of the Faculty of Education of a university, the self-efficacy beliefs towards museum education score were above the average. There was no difference between students' personal characteristics such as age, gender, and place of residence and their self-efficacy beliefs about museum education. On the other hand, it was determined that the variables such as the class, department, taking museum lessons and visiting the museum affected the students' self-efficacy beliefs towards museum education.

In line with these results;

-Museums should be institutions that should be included in education and training, as out-of-school learning environments, as places that train students, make them think, and complement the knowledge learned at school with permanent learning by offering different perspectives, and they should ensure continuity in their teaching function,

-Museum education course should be compulsory in teacher training departments and this course should be given by museum educators who are experts and competent in their fields.

-Museum education practices that will contribute to the professional development process in teacher training faculties should be addressed with a multidisciplinary approach that will be supported by different activities to be designed or methods and techniques to be used regarding the achievements in the curriculum, by associating them with different disciplines.

-Museum education self-efficacy studies should be carried out with large-scale studies.

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